

WAYS TO DEVELOP CREATIVE ABILITIES OF LANGUAGE LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

Developing the creative ability of native language learners, increasing their verbal and written creative activities, and encouraging them to become creative people is an important task. This includes teaching them effective writing and speaking practice, as well as developing a creative approach to meetings and developing comedy talent.

A creative approach allows native language learners to tap into their creative potential by changing their interests and giving them new, timeless strengths. For this, the teacher should organize activities for the development of the student's creative imagination, analytical and compositional abilities. For example, through vocabulary, speaking and story games, students are encouraged to learn to express themselves. Also, giving them opportunities to read school library approach literature, organize creative conversations and meetings, and contribute to the expression of their thoughts through tolerant words and rules is important in developing conformity to their creative approach. Increasing writing and speaking practice is a positive way to strengthen the creativity of native language learners. These indicators are related to the abilities of mothers and can be rented to them. To achieve this goal, teachers can improve students' writing practices by teaching them to write articles, create literature reviews on relevant topics, and evaluate reading-text content in relation to literature.

Encouraging creative people is an important part of a community's talent pool. For this, it is necessary to increase the creative approach to native language learners. This is done by supporting them with speaking and writing experiences, giving them opportunities to explore, critique and call out their own ideas. These metrics allow them to self-reflect, find new approaches, and improve their performance. Also, with the help of creative approaches, it is possible to improve the ability of students to coordinate their own difficulties, to consult and call, as well as to be creative and work effectively. In order to develop the creativity of native language learners, we need to understand the importance of increasing effective writing and speaking practices, increasing the creative approach in meetings, and encouraging them to be

creative people. These methods allow students to be creative people, express themselves and realize their ideas. This helps to develop their creativity and helps them to develop their creative potential. A creative approach is one of the most important ways to develop the creativity of native language learners. Mother tongue serves as the main tool for expressing one's thoughts and conveying one's thoughts to others. Therefore, learning and developing a creative approach becomes important in the social and professional life of each individual.

First of all, native language learners need to use their words correctly and sincerely. This is necessary for them to express their thoughts and communicate with others. For this, you can use opportunities such as reading books, writing articles and attending communication courses. Second, native language learners should also independently use the literature that history creates. Literature gives a person a sense of victory and serves as an important source for his creative development. Another way to develop a creative approach is to use historical articles and programs. This requires native speakers to use their words correctly and sincerely. This is necessary for them to express their thoughts and communicate with others. For this, you can use opportunities such as reading books, writing articles and attending communication courses.

Second, native language learners should also independently use the literature that history creates. Literature has a person's feelings of victory and victory and serves as an important source for the development of creativity. Another way to develop a creative approach is to use historical articles and programs. This increases the creativity of native language learners and makes them more curious about news. In today's world, the importance of learning the mother tongue is very high. Learning one's mother tongue is an important way to develop one's creative abilities. This is necessary for each person to express his thoughts and communicate with the world.

A native language learner will acquire and communicate with other cultures by learning different languages. This affects his thoughts and views of victory. For example, when a person knows English well, he can communicate with international trade relations and find a job for them. In addition, the native language learner is important for a person's development in the creative field. Through the mother tongue, we can express our thoughts and convey them to other people. This reveals our creative potential. Also, native language learners can develop themselves by expressing themselves to others. This allows them to convey their thoughts, ideas and victories to others. In particular, ways to develop creative abilities of native language learners are of great importance. Through these ways we can express our ideas and have the opportunity to use them at the international level. Together with the mother tongue, it reveals our creative potential and makes us a person who influences other people. Also, native language learners will be able to convey their vision of victory to others. It is also important for their development in the creative field.

Synthesis: Ways to develop the creativity of native language learners are very important. Through these channels, we will be able to express our ideas and use them internationally. The role of creative approach in society is very important. Native language learners should develop in this way. They increase their creativity by using words correctly and sincerely, using literature and historical articles. This is necessary for their success in social and professional life.

References:

1. State educational standard and curriculum of general secondary education. Mother tongue. Literature. Uzbek language (for schools where education is conducted in other languages). Tashkent. "Sharq" publishing-printing concern.
2. "Law on Education" of the Republic of Uzbekistan. September 23, 2020
3. Karima Kasimova, Safo Matchonov, Khalida Gulomova, Sharofat Yoldosheva, Sharoljon Sariyev " Methodology of mother tongue teaching" Tashkent "Nasir" publishing house. 2009
4. A. Gulomov, M. Kadirov, M. Ernazarova, et al. Methodology of mother tongue teaching. - T.: "Science and technology", 2012